

Study of Blister Initiation and Growth in High-Temperature Polyimide Composites

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ABSTRACT

Moisture trapped within polyimide composite parts during rapid heating can lead to plasticization, hydrolysis, and blistering. These phenomena have prompted several initiatives to develop an understanding of the mechanisms responsible for and consequences of hygrothermal degradation. In particular, the initiation and growth of blisters during heating of saturated polyimides is investigated, as well as rates of moisture diffusion at elevated temperatures.

KEY WORDS: Blister, Diffusion, High-Temperature Polyimides, Hygrothermal Performance

1. INTRODUCTION

In advanced air vehicle designs, it is desirable to utilize high-temperature organic matrix composites, HTOMCs in and around jet engines to increase the thrust-to-weight ratio. The service environment of these materials can be broadly summarized as consisting of four stages. First the material is exposed to the ambient environment when moisture is absorbed while not in service, second the material can be subjected to rapid heating rates of greater than 20-50°C/min when operation is initiated, third the material is subjected to prolonged exposure at high temperatures ranging from 230-370°C, and fourth the material is returned back to ambient conditions. Under such operating conditions it is possible for parts to develop blisters which are caused by high pressure steam generated by outgassing of adsorbed water.

Studies conducted by Cornelia, and others (1-3) have shown that during rapid heating moisture trapped in thick polyimide matrix composites can lead to plasticization, hydrolysis, and blistering.

The purpose of this research is to improve upon the methodologies currently used for predicting steam pressure-induced delamination. One such method is presented in MIL-HDBK-17 (4) where laminates of the desired part thickness are preconditioned to equilibrium at four relative humidity levels. These panels are then exposed to the mission time-temperature profiles. Samples are heated to a range of temperatures and then c-scanned to determine if a delamination has occurred. An envelope of safe operation for that particular laminate thickness can then be developed which plots exposure temperature versus initial equilibrium moisture content.

The authors of this paper propose a more fundamental approach whereby a moisture diffusion model is developed to predict the moisture distribution throughout the laminate as a function of part thickness and time-temperature history. The envelope of safe operation is defined as the maximum actual moisture content in the laminate (generally located in the midplane) plotted versus the blister initiation temperature. The blister initiation temperature is determined by monitoring part thickness during

heating. This modeling approach will allow designers to explore parts of varying thickness and multiple thermal cycles with minimal resources.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Materials Neat resin samples of a high-temperature, fluorinated polyimide, AFR700B were prepared with nominal thicknesses of 1.4 mm, 2.1 mm, 3.0 mm, and 3.8 mm. In addition composites were evaluated consisting of a similar polyimide, PMR-II-50 with T650-35/8HS fabric.

2.2 Environmental Conditioning Samples were saturated in a humidity cabinet at 29.4°C/85RH to equilibrium.

2.3 Moisture Diffusion Determination Weight loss as a function of time and temperature was determined using a Cahn TG-171 microbalance with rectangular specimens (25.4mm x 12.7mm). Measurements were conducted with a 40 cc/min nitrogen gas purge stream using heating rates of 2, 5, 15, 20 and 50°C/min to 400°C, and isothermal holds were conducted at 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, and 300°C/min with a ramp rate of 50°C/min.

2.4 Blister Onset Determination The most direct method found for determining the onset of blister formation was thickness measurement. This measurement was taken on specimens measuring 12.7mm x 12.7mm (neat resin) or 38mm x 38mm (composites) during various temperature ramps and holds. The measurement was taken in real-time by placing the sample between parallel plate fixtures of a Rheometrics RDS-II and correlating the normal force transducer with displacement or thickness change.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Temperature-Dependent Mass Diffusivity Model of Water in Resin and Composite

A series of desorption (drying) experiments under isothermal conditions were performed in a Cahn microbalance. A resin sample saturated at 29.4°C and 85% relative humidity, which contained 3.69 wt% moisture, was heated at about 50°C/min to the desired constant temperature in the balance, and the weight change throughout the drying process was recorded. The weight loss in terms of fraction of saturation (w) plotted against the square root of time over half thickness of the sample (\sqrt{t}/b) yields a curve with an initial straight portion. The slope of this straight portion of the curve is related to the diffusivity (D) for Fickian diffusion (5):

$$D = \frac{\pi}{4} \left(\frac{w_2 - w_1}{\sqrt{t_2}/b - \sqrt{t_1}/b} \right)^2,$$

where D is diffusivity; t is time; b is the half thickness of the sample; and w is the fraction of saturation. Data suggest that the Fickian diffusion model is valid up to the point of sample blistering. From these diffusivity data, shown in Figure 1, an Arrhenius expression for the temperature-dependent diffusivity has been determined to be:

$$\text{Neat Resin: } D = \exp(-10.56 + 1859.65/T - 1132735/T^2)$$

$$\text{Composite: } D = \exp(-12.82 + 261282/T - 1199024/T^2)$$

where the mass diffusivity, D , is in cm^2/s and the temperature, T , in Kelvin.

A one-dimensional model for temperature and moisture concentration distributions was constructed to predict the moisture content for a flat panel undergoing a temperature cycle. Although for the thickest (3.96 mm) sample at the highest heating rates (up to $50^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ before reaching isothermal condition in the Cahn balance, or when heated at $20^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ ramp), up to a 15-degree temperature differential could exist in the sample; inclusion of heat transfer did not always improve the accuracy of the model. The model was therefore simplified by eliminating the temperature distribution computations. The predictive capability is verified by comparing the predicted to the measured moisture content during drying in the Cahn balance. Typical results are shown in Figures 2 and 3. For the isothermal cases, conducted on samples of varying thickness, the maximum error is 0.07 (fraction of saturation). Of the cases where drying was conducted under various constant temperature ramp rates, the maximum error is slightly higher at about 0.1.

3.2 Blister Initiation and Growth Mechanisms The initiation of a blister depends on four principle criteria: 1) moisture content, 2) resin stress-strain behavior, 3) temperature, and 4) void size. As an upper estimate of steam pressure the pressure of saturated steam may be used. This pressure increases rapidly with temperature, increasing from 2 MPa (290 psi) at 200°C to 9 MPa (1300 psi) at 300°C . It is nearly impossible to measure the resin stress-strain behavior under hot wet conditions because samples dry so quickly at 300°C , however Figure 4 illustrates the change in tensile stress-strain behavior of a dry sample after hydrolytic degradation at only 150°C exposure to saturated steam. One can imagine that the yield stress of the resin is significantly lower under hot wet conditions. When the resin stress caused by steam pressure in a void exceeds the yield stress of the resin, voids in the resin will coalesce into a large blister or delamination.

A model for the maximum stress at the surface of a spherical void under internal pressure is derived by Timoshenko and Goodier (6) where:

$$\sigma_{\max} = \frac{p}{2} \frac{2a^3 + b^3}{b^3 - a^3}$$

p = void pressure
 a = void radius
 b = outer radius

This relation shows that as void size increases and for voids located near each other the maximum resin stress increases rapidly. Figures 5-7 illustrate this growth mechanism for steam induced blistering of a composite. Figure 5 shows a cross-section of a composite which was saturated with moisture then heated rapidly until it blistered. The blister occurs at the midplane where the moisture content is the highest (sample dries outside first while heating). Figure 6 shows the surface of the blistered area. It is interesting to note the splits between fibers and the pattern on the surface which follows the warp and fill yarns of the fabric. Figure 7 shows that the resin at the blistered surface has been transformed into a foam with a large variance in void size. Thin walls separating voids indicates that the resin underwent severe plastic deformation during the blister process.

3.3 Temperature-Moisture Operation Envelope Blistering occurs when there is sufficient moisture in the resin and when the temperature is high enough for the steam pressure to exceed the yield stress of the material. It follows that a temperature-moisture concentration envelope may be developed that delineates conditions under which blistering would not occur for safe operation of the part. This envelope was developed by heating moisture-saturated samples at various temperature ramp rates and observing the thickness change during the process. Samples that exceeded the temperature limit at a given moisture concentration would blister and result in a more rapid change in thickness. An RDS was

used for thickness measurements with typical results shown in Figure 8. With a relatively slow heating rate of 1°C/minute we see that the sample began to expand at 280°C and blistered at 300°C. This method was used to determine the onset temperature of blistering. The calculated moisture content of the sample at the mid-plane is also shown in Figure 8. At the point of initial expansion or void growth the moisture content is about 0.5 weight percent.

For the determination of moisture content in the sample, the diffusion model was employed to predict the moisture distribution based on the time-temperature drying cycle a sample went through. We used results from eight cases of drying 3.8 mm thick samples at temperature ramp rates of 5, 6, 7.5, 10, and 20°C/min to establish the envelope. These eight drying curves are shown in Figure 9, each terminating with a square marker that marks the temperature and predicted centerline moisture content at the onset of blistering. These square markers form the envelope of safe operation which is shown as the thick curve in Figure 9. Drying curves under the envelope represent conditions of safe operation that would not lead to blistering, while those which cross the envelope would lead to blistering. To verify the results, twenty cases with sample thicknesses of 2.1, 3.0, and 3.8 mm were run at temperature ramp rates from 4 to 40°C/min, in some cases with intermediate holds of various durations at various temperatures. These results are also plotted in Figure 9. Curves terminating with a circle represent samples that blistered at the temperature indicated by the marker. It can be seen that although most of the observed blistering onset temperatures are higher than those predicted, the envelope is quite reliable in predicting the safe operating zone. The fact that several of the trial cases blistered at higher than predicted temperatures stems from the condition that the process is also time dependant and during rapid heating rates there is less time for void formation. Figure 10 illustrates the difference in blister onset between composites which contain some voids versus neat resin samples which are nearly void free. The solid curve depicts the blister envelope described for Figure 9 while the large squares depict blister conditions for the composite. We see that the composite blistered at lower temperatures for the same moisture content as the neat resin, however for both material forms 240°C seems to be the temperature where blistering becomes a concern.

4. CONCLUSIONS

Data derived from isothermal desorption of saturated AFR700B neat resin samples were used to generate a temperature-dependent mass diffusivity model for water in AFR700B. The model is used to predict the moisture content of a sample undergoing a temperature cycle. A method for determining the temperature for the onset of blister formation in a polyimide sample by monitoring the sample thickness was also developed. These data can then be used to construct a temperature-moisture operation envelope which can be applied by part designers to determine if a part of a given thickness and initial moisture content is likely to blister while undergoing a particular thermal cycle.

5. REFERENCES

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Figure 1. Mass diffusivity of water for neat resin and composite versus temperature.

Figure 2. Measured (markers) and predicted (curves) moisture content in 3.0 mm thick samples undergoing isothermal drying at different temperatures.

Figure 3. Measured (markers) and predicted (curves) moisture content in samples of different thicknesses undergoing isothermal drying at 100°C.

Figure 4. Tensile stress-strain curves at 300°C of AFR700B resin after aging in saturated steam at 150°C.

Figure 5. Cross-section of T650-35/PMR-II-50 after blister; cut through center of the specimen.

Figure 6. Blister surface indicating processing voids and steam induced voids and splits.

Figure 7. Enlargement of composite blister surface.

Figure 8. Expansion curve of saturated T650-35/PMR-II-50 composite while heating at 1°C/minute.

Figure 9. Temperature-Moisture content envelope for AFR700B resin under atmospheric pressure. Blistering occurs if the drying curve cuts across the envelope.

Figure 10. Composite blister results compared to neat resin blister envelope.